

Child Abuse and Neglect in the Media

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Abstract

This paper examines the role of the media about child abuse and child protection and argues that the media have not played essential task in placing the problem of child abuse in the minds of the public and on the political agenda. This paper also tries to find out the reasons for the neglect in the social media regarding the child abuse.

Role of Social Media

Social media networks can be a key avenue for sharing messages and educating the public about the importance of preventing child abuse and neglect. Centres for Disease Control and Prevention (2016) Offers a social media toolkit designed to provide guidance and to share lessons learned from integrating social media into CDC health communication campaigns, activities, and emergency response efforts. The guide includes information on how to get started using social media, developing governance, determining which social media channels to use, and how to create a social media strategy.

Definition

Child abuse, it may be argued, is no different. According to Goddard (1994): “Every development in knowledge of the problem of child abuse has been accompanied by disagreements about definitions to be used, the incidence of the problem, theoretical approaches to causation, the perpetrators of abuse, the effects on victims, efficient approaches to practice, the adequacy of child protection policies, and the appropriateness of methodologies chosen to ascertain the ‘truth’ about all of the above.”

Discourses of Child Abuse: Media, Professional and Human Rights

The conceptual language of child abuse takes some distinct discursive forms. First, there is the descriptive language of moral condemnation contained in traditional words like ‘cruelty,’ ‘neglect,’ ‘ill treatment,’ ‘indecency,’ ‘incest’ and, latterly, ‘torture,’ ‘grooming,’ and ‘exploitation,’ that have framed popular media conceptualizations of child abuse. This is the language adopted by the media in reporting child abuse cases. It reflects to the public its own moral outrage and condemnation, which some commentators

argue can form moral panics (Fitzgibbon, 2012). Second, during the 1960s the professionalization of child protection led to the emergence of a new medico-legal language (physical abuse, neglect, emotional abuse and sexual abuse), which has become the dominant official discourse (Kempe and Kempe, 1978). This discourse is articulated in official guidelines, procedural manuals, professional training and student texts. The third discursive form is the language of universal human rights, which has challenged traditional thinking about childhood. Human rights discourse emerged out of the atrocities associated with the Second World War and the emergence of totalitarian societies. Article 1 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948) boldly proclaimed ‘all human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights’. The UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989) became the first international treaty to improve basic standards regarding the treatment of children. Also, the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) has established basic standards within the European Union regarding the treatment of citizens, which are enforced by the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR).

Public Response

All three discourses inform public responses to child abuse in quite distinct ways in case reportage. The mass media tends to use the populist language of moral outrage and condemnation. For example, in the UK trial of Daniel Pelka, a four-year-old abused and killed by his parents, the Daily Mail (1 August 2013) declared ‘the Polish monster who tortured and killed his four-year-old stepson had been jailed in this country three times ... But despite his serial offending he was never put on a plane back to Poland.’ The Daily Express (4 August 2013) informed its readers ‘Daniel Pelka’s evil mother is being cruel.

Poverty

The mass media’s reportage stands in sharp contrast to the medico-legal language of public enquiries. The Ryan Report (2009), which was examining a historical event in the sense that its investigation of child abuse in Irish industrial and reformatory schools was about institutions that have been closed for many years, chose to adopt a medico-legal approach: physical abuse, neglect, emotional abuse and sexual abuse. While physical abuse was the dominant mode of abuse identified by the survivors in their evidence, sexual abuse featured heavily in media reportage, partly because of the moral paradox of clergy sexually abusing children, which became a media ‘angle.’ Finally, the human rights approach to the conceptualization of child abuse is part of a humanistic discourse that challenges unaccountable adult power. It confronts society with much deeper questions that cannot be easily accommodated in media conceptualizations. The media plays a key role in leading the debate for constitutional change through its reportage of the inquiries’ findings. However, there are profound issues arising from plural childhoods, in which many children become victims of child abuse because of poverty, which the media does not address.

Parental Employment Status and Child Abuse

Family structure and parental employment status matter as well. An increase from 10 percent to 15 percent in the fraction of children with a working mother and absent father is predicted to increase substantiated cases of maltreatment by 21 percent. Likewise, an increase from 10 percent to 15 percent in the fraction of children with two unemployed parents is expected to increase maltreatment by 26 per cent. However, children with absent fathers and non-working mothers do not appear to be at higher risk for maltreatment than children with two working parents, or a working father and non-working mother.

Absent fathers, unemployed fathers, and increased poverty are all associated with increased maltreatment. Poverty has a bigger impact on neglect than on physical abuse, though. If single mothers work, child maltreatment is considerably more likely, possibly because single working mothers are more neglectful or abusive, or because their children are left in the care of someone who is neglectful or abusive. This raises the issue of the impact of welfare benefit cuts on child maltreatment. Where welfare benefits are relatively high, mothers may be more able to stay home and look after their children.

The Media, Child Abuse and Civil Society

While it is undoubtedly selective with the news, the mass media has had a powerful influence in augmenting children’s rights within civil society, simply by reporting child abuse. Survivors of child abuse become the spokespersons. Their narratives enable us to assemble an account of the child’s historic experience in care. Inevitably, the presentation of the issues shapes the public response - demanding more effective services for children. But there are also deeper issues involved, notably the use and abuse of adult power over children that tend to be framed in terms of accountability within the public realm. Justice must be done and seen to be done. This is, of course, right and proper. There is, however, a missing link in this nexus, which centres on the role of civil society in framing social and moral discourse of adult-child power relations. The socio-cultural context of the debate is often lost in the public discourse of condemnation and denial.

Neglect in Tamilnadu Magazines

A popular magazine called Anantha vikatan published a series called “aanpaal,penpal”. The magazine spoke about the general exploitations done to the female in a superficial manner. At the same time the co-magazine of it called the junior vikatan discussed the major reasons for the neglect of the news in media. The most circulated magazine is Anantha vikatan when compared to junior vikatan. If the information has been given through the most circulated and common journal, most of the public would have known about the deteriorative effects of the problem. But, there is always hidden information regarding the news in our media, both in the printed media and electronic media. They are not pointing out the criminals with their forefinger, even after knowing the criminals. In some cases, the pointed out criminals are focused only for certain time, and the media are conveniently trying to turn the concentration of the public to some other information.

Children Homes in Tamilnadu

The government has closed 500 homes since 2011, citing mismanagement, a lack of registration and misconduct but human rights groups say abuse is rife across the 1,500 government and state institutions. Rights groups have long complained that most children’s homes are poorly regulated, not inspected often enough, and that many privately-run institutions can operate without a license leaving thousands of children open to mistreatment. The scope of the problem was outlined in a petition filed in Chennai High Court by A Narayanan, the director of advocacy group CHANGE INDIA. “Not a week passes without news of neglect, physical violence such as torture and branding with iron, sexual abuse including rape, murder and suicides in child care homes in Tamil Nadu,” the affidavit said. But this news was not focused by our media, even though the government channel like DD podhigai. The media now –a – days are widely used for spreading the information what the owners of the particular channel wants to spread. The channel owners use their channel as the advertising provision, as they know it is the most effective and efficient way of capturing the attention of the viewers. The major reason for neglect is that, most of the channel owners are related to any one of the political party, either directly or indirectly. They are taking at most care that, any of their news should not affect their political party at any cost.

Pull of Good Education

Child rights campaigners estimate that 200,000 children in Tamil Nadu are residents of private orphanages, state-supported care homes, Islamic madrassas, temples and hostels. Many children are not orphans but placed in institutional care by their parents too poor to feed, clothe and shelter them. “An increasing number of these children are from marginalized families,” CHANGEindia’s Narayanan told the Thomson Reuters Foundation.

“The parents are lured by the pull of good education and promise of better care for their children. They are relying on institutional care.” Various reports submitted to the government in the past five years have warned of shoddy conditions in children’s homes - from poor lighting and cramped accommodation to violence. In the majority of reported cases, the perpetrators of abuse have been wardens, watchmen, cooks and other staff.

Tamil Nadu government officials have said in court that they were looking at the recommendations made by campaigners, which include better monitoring of homes, individual child care plans, more counsellors and encouraging the idea of foster care. In one of the latest closures, state authorities shut down after another privately-run institution housing 32 children near the port city of Chennai last month after complaints of mismanagement. “These organisations have become organized rackets,” Narayanan said. “There are many organisations which have a valid registration but no child care plan, no counsellors and no expertise on how to fulfil a child’s emotional needs.”

So, here comes the religious faith to be the reason for neglect in the media. If a particular organization run by the particular religion is under consideration of the problem, the media about the concerned religion would try to neglect the news. Not only ending with that, but they would also try to disperse the concentration of the public towards some other news.

Misrepresented

Children rescued in a separate operation on June 30, from an institution in Tambaram, near Chennai, described being made to clean toilets and eat “unpalatable” food, according to RN Manikandan, chairman of a local child welfare committee. He also said the children shared the same space as residents of a nursing home run by the same organisation, which also caused concern. Child welfare committee members also raised questions about the babies they found in the premises during an earlier inspection, who are now missing.

According to Narayanan’s affidavit, many children from poor families were shown as destitute orphans in the records and “paraded” before potential adoptive parents and donors funding these homes. In December, an unregistered home in Tiruchy was taken over by the social welfare department after a court directive. The home had 90 children in its custody but no records with any government agency.

A wave of claims by people saying they were the children’s parents prompted a local court to rule that all the children should undergo DNA testing to establish their real families. “Not all children in these homes are in need of the care they promise,” said Andrew Sesuraj, a director at the Tamil Nadu Child Rights Observatory. He said there was no need for so many homes. “Foster care or support for the families to enable them to send their children to school is what is required.”

Conclusion

The neglect in the media could be wound up, not only by the expectations of the public, but the channel owners and the editors and the publishers of the printed media should have a motive to spread the truth. This neglect in the media paves the way for the criminals to be bold enough to do the crimes. When the neglect regarding child abuse has been ploughed out, then our planet would be a safe place the tender little human beings to live for.

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